

ORGANIZATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE QUALITY CONTROL SYSTEM IN QMS DURING THE PRODUCTION OF PRODUCTS OF FOOD INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7193666>

Abstract. *Importance of improving and enhance the quality of products is priceless. Consumer requirements for products and services are the main requirements for the quality of products. In this case, the introduction of a quality management system is a complex and time-consuming process, which involves the organization of all work and affects various aspects of the enterprise's activities and the quality of management systems. Day by day, the requirements for quality and safety are increasing, since the requirements for standards are also becoming more stringent. This article analyzes the quality of the control system of Management, describes the advantages of the system, as well as the effects that enterprises receive in its implementation.*

Keywords: *quality management system, quality control mechanism, planning management, quality requirements .*

ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ И АНАЛИЗ СИСТЕМЫ КОНТРОЛЯ КАЧЕСТВА В СМК ПРИ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ ПРОДУКЦИИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ ПИЩЕВОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ

Аннотация. *Важность улучшения и повышения качества продукции бесценна. Требования потребителей к товарам и услугам являются основными требованиями к качеству продукции. В данном случае внедрение системы менеджмента качества является сложным и трудоемким процессом, который предполагает организацию всей работы и влияет на различные аспекты деятельности предприятия и качество систем менеджмента. День ото дня требования к качеству и безопасности повышаются, поскольку требования к стандартам также становятся более жесткими. В данной статье анализируется качество системы контроля управления, описываются преимущества системы, а также эффекты, которые предприятия получают при ее внедрении.*

Ключевые слова: *система менеджмента качества, механизм контроля качества, управленческое планирование, требования к качеству.*

INTRODUCTION

The success and efficiency of the development of a company depends on the solution of the problem of organizing and implementing quality control. The quality control system is a set of methods and means that ensure the entry of products that meet the established requirements. Implementation of the QMS (quality management system) contributes to the achievement of high results in the field of quality control.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The company's motto is: "Control today is a guarantee for high quality tomorrow." And the main objectives of the policy in the field of quality control are:

- quality control of products at all stages of the product life cycle; – control of technological discipline;
- control of QMS functioning;

– monitoring compliance with the requirements of standards, specifications, constructor documentation, technical documentation in the QMS processes, including through both internal audits by in-house specialists and external control by certification bodies and testing laboratories.

The modern approach to quality management has evolved over several decades. Their formation and dynamics are due to both all-Russian and republican trends in socio-economic development. The mechanism of quality management and quality control, as an integral part, is being continuously improved at the enterprise. The managers of the enterprise decided to move from the quality system (QS) to the QMS. 2 specialists and 3 QMS internal audit inspectors were trained, the company's quality policy was clarified in accordance with the company's goals and commitments to continuous improvement, measurable goals were set, and areas of QMS activity were defined. In order to prepare the enterprise for certification, internal audits are currently being carried out according to annually developed plans, based on the results of which a report is drawn up.

A corrective action plan was developed for identified nonconformities. The focus of the company is on the quality of both products and quality management processes. Commitment to the idea of quality is reflected in the Company's Quality Policy and it is very important that the responsibility and management of the work related to the functioning and improvement of the QMS has been assumed by the top management of the enterprise. The enterprise uses a system of controlled identified and interacting processes.

RESULTS

All processes are divided into four main categories: management processes; resource management processes; product life cycle processes; measurement, analysis and improvement processes. Each process defined in the QMS is described in the form of a documented procedure (enterprise standard), which includes a description of the process and a process map (a graphical representation of the process in the form of interrelated symbols identifying individual processes). The enterprise uses methods for monitoring, measuring and controlling QMS processes to demonstrate the ability of processes to achieve planned results with correction if the results are not achieved. Monitoring and analysis of information received from external consumers is carried out on an ongoing basis. Internal audits are carried out, which is one of the ways to measure the effectiveness of the QMS

The organization also monitors and measures products to verify compliance with the requirements established for them and also includes: input control and testing, control during production (operational and acceptance control), final control and testing. Thus, quality control is provided at all stages of the production cycle of manufacturing and carried out by the direct executors of production operations.

The most important goals in the QMS of the enterprise are:

- provision of guarantees to the customer to ensure the stipulated level of product quality;
- Creation of confidence in the management of the organization that the assigned tasks in the field of quality will be fulfilled. The main tasks of the QMS are:

- active management of all processes that affect product quality, as a means of preventing the occurrence of inconsistencies;

- organization of effective control (assessment) of conformity products to consumer requirements and organization of control over compliance of processes;

- normative and methodological guidance for quality assurance.

- QMS is based on the principles of TQM (total quality management)
- priority satisfaction of needs and requirements of consumers to product quality;
- distribution of responsibility and powers among all levels of management of organizations;
- employees of all levels
- the basis of the organization, their full involvement in the work to ensure product quality, encouraging the initiative and creativity of performers;
- management of activities and related resources as a process;
- closed-loop process control
- from the requirements of the consumer through the implementation of processes with the introduction of feedback to determine satisfaction with the results;
- continuous improvement of the organization's activities;
- making decisions based on facts;
- mutually beneficial relationships with suppliers to enhance the ability of both parties to create value.

Thus, the current QMS at food industry enterprises is a set of governing bodies and management objects interacting with the help of material, technical and information means in managing product quality at all stages of its life cycle.

The effectiveness of the QMS operating at the enterprise largely depends on the organization and functioning of the control system. The effectiveness of the current QMS is analyzed by management through meetings. The results of control (input, in the production process, final), the results of internal checks and corrective actions, claims, suggestions, inspection control are subject of analyzing.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the analysis, a protocol is drawn up, on the basis of which a plan for improving the QMS and corrective actions are developed for identified inconsistencies. Quality control in an enterprise begins with planning and designing quality based on customer requests and market research results. The project is evaluated at all stages, from the drafting of the terms of reference and ending with the release of products.

Based on the results of the work, an act will be drawn up, a decision is made on the production. Then control is carried out at the stage of production planning. Specialists monitor compliance with the requirements of technological processes. In case of detection of non-conforming products, they are immediately placed in non-conformity isolators, and the responsibility lies with the heads of departments, who are notified about this. Insulated products are examined to determine the cause of the nonconformity and a decision is made on reworking, further use or disposal.

Further, all reports are summarized, analyzed and a single report is compiled for the month, half year, year. Thus, the enterprise has a complex structure of departments involved in the control process, which is carried out in order to prevent the release of products that do not meet the established requirements.

CONCLUSIONS

Quality control is preventive in nature and is based on the principles of the inadmissibility of including materials, components, equipment in the production process that deviate from the requirements established in the technical documentation, as well as the full

responsibility of the direct contractor for the quality of products and the quality of performance of their duties.

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